

Causes that generate social debt in agile software development distributed teams

Table 2: Causes that generate social debt in distributed team.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
Factor: Communication	
CED1	Loss or distortion of information (incommunicability) [PS4, PS9, PS32].
CED2	Informality Excess: absence of informative protocols [PS5, PS32].
CED3	Bottleneck: one person intermediates all critical communications [PS6, PS32].
CED4	Asynchronous communication due to time differences [PS24].
CED5	Years of mismanaged experience and lack of communication skills assessment [PS12, PS33, PS41].
CED6	Lack of cross-cutting information exchange and lack of awareness of existing community smells [PS1, PS24, PS32].
CED7	Communication and coordination difficulties associated with language differences, time zones and geographical distance [PS20, PS24].
CED8	Presence of informal networks that hinder structured communication [PS9, PS27].
CED9	Absence of explicit communication and Missing Links [PS32, PS37, PS38].
CED10	High proportion of developers who collaborate without interacting directly [PS9, PS38].
CED11	Poor management of information flow (Black Cloud) [PS9, PS32, PS41].
CED12	Lack of efficient feedback channels [PS32, PS45].
Factor: Collaboration and social structure	
CED13	Newbie Free-riding: new members without guidance and support generate overload for others [PS5, PS8, PS9].
CED14	Team size and lack of balance in its composition [PS11, PS24, PS41].
CED15	Priggish Members: authoritarian or excessively demanding attitudes [PS8].
CED16	Institutional Isomorphism: imitation among sub-communities that inhibits innovation [PS8, PS24].
CED17	Hyper-Community: hyper-connected groups with groupthink [PS9, PS24].
CED18	Isolated subgroups, organizational silos and negative power dynamics (Organizational Silo, Prima-donna Effect) [PS9, PS24, PS30, PS34].
CED19	Isolation and lack of collaboration (Lone Wolf) [PS9, PS24, PS41].
CED20	Lack of consensus (Dissensus) and changes that fragment collaborative structures (Dispersion) [PS9, PS42].
CED21	Environments with rigid hierarchical structures that limit open communication [PS24].
Factor: Coordination	
CED22	Inconsistency in personnel availability.
CED23	Lack of time synchronization [PS2, PS21].
CED24	Informal or inadequate use of coordination and collaboration tools [PS9, PS21, PS23].
CED25	Lack of face-to-face or synchronized meetings [PS22].
CED26	Lack of synchronization of tasks, meetings, and information transfer [PS26].
CED27	Lack of formal coordination and knowledge intermediaries (Radio Silence) [PS9, PS21, PS34, PS37].
CED28	Lack of formal synchronization mechanisms [PS21,].
CED29	Inadequate or limited use of collaborative tools such as JIRA or Slack [PS21].
CED30	Lack of clear coordination mechanisms [PS40].
CED31	Hybrid or distributed teams facing inclusion, coordination and collaboration challenges [PS21].
Factor: Socio-technical Congruence	
CED32	Deficient technological infrastructure and limited teleworking experience [PS2, PS10].
CED33	Disconnection between architecture and development teams [PS3, PS10].
CED34	Methodological incompatibilities between sites [PS4, PS10].

Id	Cause and Primary studies
CED35	DevOps Clash: conflicts between development and operations in different geographic locations [PS5, PS9, PS10].
CED36	Accumulation of technical debt [PS10, PS15].
CED37	Differences in tools and technologies between sites [PS10, PS26].
CED38	Disconnection between architects and technical teams [PS10].
CED39	Misalignment between technical decisions and business needs [PS10, PS39].
CED40	Refactoring that complicates code understanding (Class Cognition) and centralized maintenance by a few developers (Code Red) [PS32, PS43].
CED41	Non-aligned technical and social units, aggravated by centralized decisions and lack of situational awareness [PS10, PS45].
Factor: Cultural and organizational factors	
CED42	Distributed environments with time, cultural, linguistic and language differences [PS1, PS24].
CED43	Lack of inclusive and active leadership [PS1–PS3, PS25].
CED44	Low intrinsic motivation, perception of wage injustice and emotional disconnection [PS1, PS25].
CED45	Lack of cultural alignment and inappropriate hiring [PS3, PS24].
CED46	Pressure for quick deliveries that favor "social shortcuts" [PS3].
CED47	Cultural conflicts [PS3, PS24].
CED48	Absence of institutional mechanisms such as Architecture Boards [PS4, PS23].
CED49	Cognitive Distance: social/technical/cultural differences [PS5].
CED50	Unlearning: loss of good practices due to generational diversity [PS5, PS8, PS23].
CED51	Low maturity in distributed agile methodologies [PS6, PS23].
CED52	Turnover and lack of continuity have a negative impact [PS7, PS23].
CED53	Cognitive Distance: physical, technical or cultural differences between developers [PS8].
CED54	Cookbook Development: resistance to new ways of working [PS8, PS23].
CED55	Domestic disruptions and emotional burden from the pandemic context [PS23].
CED56	Lack of confidence, conviction, stability and insufficient team experience [PS24, PS25].
CED57	Management problems and differences in cognitive styles or international approaches [PS24, PS25].
CED58	Lack of cultural understanding and alignment [PS24, PS26].
CED59	Organizational culture that favors independence without coordination [PS23].
CED60	Generational inequality and organizational complexity [PS23, PS39].
CED61	Low gender diversity [PS24, PS41].
CED62	Cultural diversity that hinders alignment of objectives and processes [PS10, PS24].